

The results are in Table 2.

Nutrient accumulation due to straw incorporation, averaged for the three water regimes, was as follows:

Nutrient	kg/ha per season
Total N	38
Available P	3
Exchangeable K	11

In 2 parallel 6-year-long field experiments, incorporation of straw produced in situ gave the identical value of 38 kg/ha per season for nitrogen added. Although the content of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium increased, yield was low with or without straw incorporation and the benefit of straw incorporation small because of zinc

deficiency and boron toxicity induced by bad irrigation water.

To ascertain whether comparable amounts of nutrients were added in other soils, the effect of straw incorporation at 5 t/ha on the nutrient status of three soils was studied outdoors in 200-liter steel drums. The soils were Luisiana clay (pH: 6.7, total N: 0.154%), Maahas clay (pH: 7.1, total N: 0.130%), and Pila clay loam (pH: 7.7, total N: 0.109%).

Nitrogen accretion varied with the soil: it was highest in Pila clay loam and least in Maahas clay. In all three soils straw incorporation significantly increased grain yield (Table 3). The increase in nutrient content on a hectare basis was as follows:

Clay	Increase (kg/ha per season)		
	Total N	Available P	Exchangeable K
Luisiana clay	43	0.3	13
Maahas clay	26	0.2	24
Pila clay loam	77	1.0	17
Mean	49	0.5	18

Incorporation of straw brought about an increase of 38 kg nitrogen and about 14 kg/ha per season of exchangeable potassium in two field experiments on Maahas clay. The corresponding increases averaged for three soils in a drum study were 49 kg N and 18 kg K.

Incorporating straw increases the natural supply of nutrients in wetland rice soils. ■

Efficient use of fertilizer nitrogen in wetland rice under poor water management

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A split application of nitrogen sometimes increases fertilizer efficiency and yields of wetland rice more than does a single basal application. But the efficiency of split-applied nitrogen depends on water management. Water-management constraints in farmers' fields include field-to-field irrigation, lack of drainage facilities, and over irrigation prompted by irregular water supply. Therefore the practice of split nitrogen application was evaluated under both controlled and uncontrolled irrigation in the 1978 wet season in five villages under the Operational Research Project, Miryalguda, Andhra Pradesh. The soil was a red sandy loam with pH 7.8-8.0 and 0.52-0.86% organic matter. Controlled irrigation (CI) involved submergence at 2- to 5-cm level through separate channels, drainage before topdressing of nitrogen, and reflooding. Uncontrolled irrigation (UI) practices were the farmers' normal heavy application of irrigation water (submergence level varying from 5 to 20 cm), field-to-field irrigation, and topdressing of nitrogen on

Effect of water management on grain yield and efficiency of urea-nitrogen applied at 100 kg N/ha. Mean of 5 experimental sites in a farmer's field. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1978 wet season.^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Yield response (kg grain/kg fertilizer N)		Recovery of fertilizer N in grain + straw (%) (Differential method)	
	CI ^b	UI ^b	CI	UI	CI	UI
Control, no N	3.6	3.1	—	—	—	—
Urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.4	23.2	13.4	40.3	21.9
NC-urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.9	23.0	18.2	29.4	24.7
NC-urea, all basal	6.7	5.6	30.7	25.1	65.9	46.5
LSD (0.05)	0.66		7.80		9.08	
CV (%)	10.00		16.50		18.05	

^a NC-urea = urea blended with neem cake (residue of *Azadirachta indica* seed after oil extraction) at 30% by weight of urea using coal tar solution. Split application = 25% basal with incorporation, 50% topdressed at active tillering stage and 25% at panicle initiation.

^b CI = controlled irrigation, UI = uncontrolled irrigation.

floodwater with no previous drainage.

All treatments required careful water management for best results (see table).

Yields decreased about 26% when split application of ordinary urea was associated with the farmers' poor management of irrigation water.

Despite poor water management, basal application of neem cake-blended urea gave yields, yield responses, and crop recovery of added nitrogen equal to those of split application of ordinary urea under ideal conditions. ■

Effect of seedling age and number per hill on grain yield of rice varieties

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Seedlings of rice varieties Pusa 2-21 and Jaya were transplanted at 20, 40, and 60 days after seeding to study the extent of yield reduction when transplanting

is delayed. To compensate for yield reduction 2, 4, or 6 seedlings/hill were transplanted. The experiment used a randomized block design with four replications. The crop was sown in wet nursery beds at the Crop Research Center, Pantnagar on 16 June in the 1977-78 wet season.

When older seedlings of short-duration Pusa 2-21 were transplanted, yield reduction was consistent regardless of